

Quinoline N-oxide Derivatives of Hexaquo cobalt (II) chloride

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Cobalt(II) forms two types of complexes, one pink octahedral and the other blue tetrahedral, as the metal chloride to quinoline N-oxide ratio is changed from 1 : 1 to 1 : 2. On heating the pink complex at 200°, another tetrahedral complex of grey-green colour and of composition different from the blue is formed. The dq and B values of the pink complex are obtained from its mull spectra. The former corresponds with the value calculated from 'average environment rule'. The complexes have been characterised by magnetic moment, infrared spectra and electronic spectra.

A FEW quinoline N-oxide complexes of oxocations of some higher valent metals¹ and hexakis (quinoline-N-oxide) complexes of Ni(II) and cobalt(II) perchlorates^{2,3} have already been reported. In this paper is described the isolation and characterisation of a pink pseudooctahedral ($\mu_{eff} = 5.20$ B.M.), one blue and another grey-green pseudotetrahedral ($\mu_{eff} = 4.60$ B.M. for both the complexes) complexes of cobalt(II). The pink pseudooctahedral complex of empirical formula $[\text{CoCl}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2(\text{QO})]$ is formed when the cobalt salt $\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and the ligand quinoline N-oxide are mixed in a mole ratio of 1 : 1. But as the ratio is changed to 1 : 2 a blue pseudotetrahedral complex of composition $\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{QO}$ results. Another pseudotetrahedral complex $[\text{CoCl}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})(\text{QO})]$ which is grey-green in colour is obtained by heating the pink complex to about 200°.

Experimental

Preparations: Quinoline N-oxide was prepared following the method of Ochiai⁴ and purified by distillation under vacuum (10 mm). An almost colourless liquid which freezes to light yellow solid at room temperature, was preserved over anhydrous CaCl_2 .

1. Chloro diaquo quinoline N-oxide cobalt(II)- μ -dichloro chloro diaquo quinoline N-oxide cobalt(II) : $\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (2.38 g, 0.01 mole) was dissolved in 5 ml of ethanol and to the solution was added 1.45 g (0.01 mole) of quinoline N-oxide also dissolved in 8 ml of ethanol and the resulting solution was kept in a boiling water bath for 30 min, at which time pink solid separated. This was filtered, washed thoroughly with ethanol and light petroleum and then dried in air. Yield 2.10 g, m.p. 250° (d) [Found, C, 34.1; H, 3.79; Cl, 23.1; N, 4.70; Co, 18.7; Calc. for $\text{Co}_2\text{Cl}_4(\text{QO})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4$; C, 34.7; H, 3.53; Cl, 22.8; N, 4.50 and Co, 18.9%].

2. Dichloro bis (quinoline N-oxide) cobalt(II) : $\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (1.19 g, 0.005 mole) was dissolved in 10 ml of ethanol and the solution was mixed with 2.9 g (0.02 mole) of quinoline N-oxide also dissolved in 10 ml of ethanol and boiled and then evaporated in a boiling water bath for half an hour and filtered,

leaving a mixture of pink and blue residue, and a blue filtrate. The residue was boiled with 15 ml of ethanol containing 0.5 g of quinoline N-oxide and filtered, when a pink residue and a blue filtrate was collected. The two blue filtrates were mixed together and evaporated in vacuum almost to dryness. The solid mass left was cooled and extracted with a solvent mixture containing 10 ml of acetone and 40 ml of benzene, boiled, cooled and filtered. The separated blue crystals were washed with benzene and vacuum dried. Yield 1.10 g, m.p. 180° [Found, C, 50.8; H, 3.51; Cl, 17.1; N, 6.79; Co, 14.3; Calc. for $\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{QO}$; C, 51.4; H, 3.33; Cl, 16.9; N, 6.67 and Co, 14.0%].

3. Aquo dichloro quinoline N-oxide cobalt (II) : The pink complex, $[\text{Co}_2\text{Cl}_4(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4(\text{QO})_2]$, in a porcelain crucible was heated in the furnace of a thermobalance. The temperature was allowed to rise upto 200°. It was then switched off and the crucible was kept there until the temperature dropped below 100°. The crucible-containing uniformly grey-green compound was taken out and stored over CaCl_2 since on exposure to moisture the original pink complex was reformed [Found, C, 36.3; H, 3.32; Cl, 24.7; N, 4.79; Co, 20.5; Calc. for $[\text{CoCl}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})(\text{QO})]$, C, 36.8; H, 3.07; Cl, 24.3; N, 4.77 and Co, 20.1%].

Magnetic measurements were made by the Gouy method, with mercury tetrathiocyanato cobaltate as a standard.

Conductivities were measured in Mullard conductivity bridge type E 7566/2.

Infrared spectra (4000-650 cm^{-1}) in Nujol mull were recorded in Perkin-Elmer infraord with sodium chloride optics. The spectra from 700-400 cm^{-1} were measured in Nujol mull in a Beckman IR 12 instrument equipped with KBr window and that from 400-200 cm^{-1} was measured in the same instrument equipped with polythelene window.

The electronic spectra were measured in Hilger UV Spectrophotometer over the range 350-950 nm.

A Chevenard's thermobalance, Type 3 of ADAMEL of Paris, was used to record the thermolysis curve upto 700°. The rate of heating was 5° per min.

The G.R. (E. Merck) quality methanol was distilled before use. Acetonitrile was kept mixed with P₂O₅ for 2 days and then distilled. The middle fractions of the solvents so purified were used for absorption and conductance measurements.

Characterisation and Discussion

The presence of water molecules in the pink complex is indicated by a O-H stretching mode at 3450 cm⁻¹ and a H-O-H bending mode at 1625 cm⁻¹ in the infrared spectra. That these water molecules are coordinated is supported by the thermolysis curve (Fig. 1) which shows that the loss of water takes place only over 118° and the resultant species is stable upto 292°. The species within the temperature range (140°-292°) is the grey-green compound, [CoCl₂(H₂O)(QO)] which is also characterised by O-H stretching and H-O-H bending modes in the same regions as mentioned above.

From the far infrared spectra, the pink complex appears to exhibit a strong cobalt-chlorine stretching band at 260 cm⁻¹ characteristic of bridging chloride⁶ and a strong band due to metal-chlorine terminal bond at 370 cm⁻¹. The complex is soluble only in water where it decomposes and so its molecular weight could not be determined. A mull spectrum

So, the elementary analyses (cf. experimental section), magnetic susceptibility measurements, infrared spectral data (specially the far IR) and the ligand field spectra clearly reveal that in all probability the pink pseudooctahedral complex is a dimer with bridging chloride ligands as depicted in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2.

The blue complex, CoCl₂2QO, undergoes solvation reaction in methanol and ethanol by the nucleophilic substitution of the halide ligands with the solvent molecules, as observed⁸ in the UO₂²⁺ and VO²⁺ complexes, and hence its electronic spectra in acetonitrile, in which such reaction occurs to a negligible extent, has been measured and is found to be characteristic of a cobalt(II) tetrahedral complex with

Fig. 1. The Thermolysis curves of (A) [CoCl₂(H₂O)₂(QO)]₂ and (B) CoCl₂2QO.

of this compound in Nujol in the visible region suggests pseudooctahedral configuration. Here the ν₃ band [⁴T_{1g}(F) → ⁴T_{1g}(P)] is split because of lower symmetry and the low intensity ν₂ band [⁴T_{1g}(F) → ⁴A_{2g}] is also observed. From these ν₂ and ν₃ bands, ligand field parameters as dq and B are calculated⁶ and the dq value so obtained corresponds to the value calculated from average environment rule⁷. The low B value indicates covalent character of metal-ligand bonds (Table 1).

TABLE 1—BAND POSITIONS AND DERIVED LIGAND FIELD PARAMETERS OF PINK COBALT (II) COMPLEX

Band heads (cm ⁻¹)	Ligand field parameters (cm ⁻¹)				
ν ₃	Average ν ₃	ν ₂	dq found	dq. calc by average environment rule	B
22,030	20,640	17,360	916	908	700
20,660					
19,230					

considerable fine-structure for spin-orbit coupling. The spectrum for the grey-green complex has also been measured in acetonitrile. The ν₃ bands [⁴A₂ → ⁴T₁(P)] of both the complexes are recorded in Table 2. For the lack of instrumental facilities, the ν₂ bands could not be measured and so the ligand

TABLE 2—THE ν₃ BANDS OF TETRAHEDRAL COBALT (II) COMPLEXES

Compound	Band heads (cm ⁻¹)	ε _{max.}	Average ν ₃ (cm ⁻¹)
CoCl ₂ 2QO	17,390	235	16,200
	16,950	240	
	15,870 (sh)	—	
	14,600	360	
[CoCl ₂ (H ₂ O)(QO)] ₂	17,390	280	16,240
	16,950	275	
	16,260 (sh)	—	
	16,000	280	
	14,600	410	

field parameters for the tetrahedral complexes could not be obtained.

The N-O stretching bands of pure quinoline N-oxide⁹⁻¹¹, which occur at 1310, 1265, 1230 [$\bar{\nu}(\text{N-O})$ + $\rho(\text{C-H})$] and 1205 cm^{-1} are shifted in the complexes (Table 3), where the N-O stretching bands are

compensates the ligand (QO) to metal σ donation. This is quite possible, because cobalt(II) bonded to a number of other essentially non π -accepting ligands delocalizes the accumulated electron density to empty anti-bonding π^* orbital of the N-oxide. However, the band around 1310 cm^{-1} is not observed in the grey-green compound.

TABLE 3— $\bar{\nu}(\text{N-O})$ AND $\delta(\text{N-O})$ OF QUINOLINE N-OXIDE COBALT (II) COMPLEXES

Band heads in cm^{-1}			Assignment
$[\text{CoCl}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2(\text{QO})_2]$	$[\text{CoCl}_2(\text{QO})_2]$	$[\text{CoCl}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})(\text{QO})]$	
1318(w)	1318(w)	1270(m)	$\bar{\nu}(\text{N-O})$
1275(w)	1268(s)	1280(sh)	
1262(s)	1214(s)	1232(w)	
1205(s)	1048(s)	1220(m)	
874(s)	880(m)	830(s)	$\delta(\text{N-O})$

invariably split, specially in the pink octahedral complex, due perhaps to the presence of non-equivalent ligands or coupling with Co-O vibration¹². The lowering of N-O bands as observed in UO_2^{2+} and VO^{2+} complexes¹ are not observed here probably because the metal to ligand (QO) π -bond

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